

Title: Population Divergence Associated with Spatial Asynchrony in Precipitation in Neotropical Frogs

Authors: Carlos E. Guarnizo¹, Paola Montoya², Ignacio Quintero³, Carlos Daniel Cadena¹

Author's institutional affiliations:

¹. Departamento de Ciencias Biológicas, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia.

². Instituto de Investigación de Recursos Biológicos Alexander von Humboldt, Bogotá, Colombia.

³. Institut de Biologie de l'École Normale Supérieure (IBENS), ENS, 75005 Paris, France.

Figure S1. Net primary productivity map at 5 x 5 decimal degrees. The values were obtained from the information generated by SEDAC at 0.25° and are given in grams of carbon (Imhoff et al. 2004). See text for details.

Figure S2. Topographic heterogeneity map at 5 x 5 decimal degrees, estimated as the variance in elevation across 1-km² grid cells. Colors towards blue indicate greater heterogeneity. See text for details.

Figure S3. Graphical summary of data of asynchrony in precipitation, genetic distance and topographic distance used in the MMRR, for 38 neotropical frog species included in the study. Horizontal dark lines in the boxes are the medians and black dots are outliers.

Figure S4. Pairwise comparisons of asynchrony in precipitation and residual genetic distance after accounting for ecological connectivity, for each of 38 species included in the analysis. We show three panels per species. The first panel (on the left bounded by blue square) is a map showing the pairwise (i.e. between localities) residuals of the relationship between ecological connectivity and genetic distances, while the second panel (on the center bounded by orange square) shows pairwise estimates of asynchrony in precipitation. For both maps, redder and thicker lines connecting localities indicate higher values. Because we tested the relationship between precipitation asynchrony and genetic distances using a multiple regression approach that controls for the effect of ecological connectivity, we map the residuals instead of the raw genetic distances. In the third panel (on the right) the small map on the top broadly indicates the geographic location of localities sampled for each species. Below, the blue histogram shows the frequency of residuals displayed on the map of the first panel, and the orange histogram shows the frequency of pairwise precipitation asynchrony comparisons displayed on the second panel (i.e., histogram colors correspond to those of the boxes in the left and right panels). The symbols at the right side of the species names [i.e., (+) and (-)] indicate the effect direction for significant relationships between genetic distance and asynchrony in precipitation. Note that our core results and conclusions are based on models involving multiple variables and account for spatial autocorrelation, and hence pairwise relationships between predictors and response variables are not direct and can be difficult to visualize. Plots are provided only to depict geographic sampling and patterns in data distribution.

